

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2021-22 academic year for MPT

ADVANCE CARDIAC LIFE SUPPORT (ACLS)

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value added course on

Advance Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)

Course Duration: 30 Hours
(for MPT 2021 Batch)

Course objectives:

1. To teach Basic life support skills, including effective chest compressions, use of a bag-mask device, and use of an AED.
2. To train in airway management.
3. To train in managing ACS and stroke.

**Venue: Srinivas University city campus
Pandeshwar
Mangaluru- 575001
Contact: 0824-2429139;
deanphysiotherapy@srinivasuniversity.edu.in**

Made with PosterMyWall.com

Course period	From June till September 2022, during 2 nd semester (15 weeks)
Duration	30 hours (2 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	MPT 1 st year postgraduates (2021 batch)

Course Objectives:

1. To provide the students necessary knowledge and skills required for organizing and carrying out entrepreneurial activities.

2. To develop the ability of analyzing and understanding business situations
3. To master the knowledge necessary to plan entrepreneurial activities.

Course Outline:

Module	Topic	Hours
1	Introduction to ACLS: ACLS Protocols, Role of Provider, ACLS Algorithms, Steps in ACLS, Materials used in ACLS Protocols. Initial Assessment: Quick Assessment, Distress Assessment, Post Assessment Callout	7
2	ACLS Basic Life Support: Initiating the chain of survival, 2020 BLS Guidelines, One Rescuer Adult ACLS CPR, 2 Rescuer Adult ACLS CPR, 1 Rescuer ACLS for Infants, 2 Rescuer ACLS for Infants. Advance Cardiac Life Support: Normal Heart Anatomy and Physiology, ACLS Rhythms and Interpretations, The ACLS Survey, Airway management, Basic Airway Adjuncts, Basic Airway Techniques, Advanced Airway Adjuncts, Roots of Access, Pharmacological Tools.	15
3	Principles of Early Defibrillation: Key to using an Automated External Defibrillator (AED). Systems of Care: Cardio Pulmonary Resuscitation, Post Cardiac Arrest Care, Acute Coronary Symptoms, Acute Stroke, The Resuscitation Team, The Education and Implementation.	4
4	ACLS Cases: Symptomatic Bradycardia. Stable and Unstable Tachycardia, Pulse less Electrical Activity Asystole, Pulse less Ventricular Tachycardia and Ventricular Fibrillation, ACLS Training Skills.	4

Attendance Policy:

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

References:

1. AHA. 2020 ACLS provider manual. American Heart Association, 2021.
2. S. Meloni. Advanced cardiac Life Support (ACLS) provider manual- a comprehensive guide covering latest guidelines. Medical creations, 2021.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

ABDULLAH (5SU21PT801)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in black ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

AISWARYA CHANDRAN (5SU21PT802)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'M. T. Lagan'.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar S'.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

AMIYA P DESSAI (5SU21PT803)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in blue ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

ARJUN PAVITHRAN T M (5SU21PT804)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in blue ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

ARYA T K (5SU21PT805)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in blue ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

AYSHA FIDHA (5SU21PT806)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'M. T. Lagan'.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar S'.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

CHAUDHARY JHANVI KETANBHAI (5SU21PT807)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'M. T. Lagan'.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar S'.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

JISHNU MOHAN M P (5SU21PT808)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in black ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

JOONA A (5SU21PT809)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in blue ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

KADAM VIDYA NARAYANRAO (5SU21PT810)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'M. T. Lagan'.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar S'.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

KEERTHANA R (5SU21PT811)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in blue ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

PAI PURVA PURUSHOTTAM (5SU21PT812)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'M. T. Lagan'.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar S'.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

PATIL SHIVANI ASHOK (5SU21PT813)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in blue ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

RAGENDHU S (5SU21PT814)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'M. T. Lagan'.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar S'.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

NAGAR RICHI RAMESHKUMAR (5SU21PT815)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in blue ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

SARA SHIVA KUMAR (5SU21PT816)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'M. T. Lagan'.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar S'.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

SHAIKH UZMA SHAKILAHMED (5SU21PT817)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in blue ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

SIDDESH G (5SU21PT818)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'M. T. Lagan'.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar S'.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

SOLANKI RISHIKESH DEVENDRABHAI (5SU21PT819)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in blue ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

SWETA PATNAIK (5SU21PT820)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'M. T. Lagan'.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar S'.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

T SUJAY KUMAR REDDY (5SU21PT821)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'M. T. Lagan'.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Rajasekar S'.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate presented to

TENZIN GYALZIN (5SU21PT822)

for successfully completing the value added course on
"Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)" conducted from
June to September 2022

TOTAL HOURS- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Tamilalagan in blue ink.

Dr. Tamilalagan
Course instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. Rajasekar S in green ink.

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean